

EFFECT OF MOISTURE EXPOSURE DURING FABRICATION ON FLAX/POLYESTER COMPOSITES

M. Miao^{1*}, N. Milanovic² and S. Z. Shen³

¹ CSIRO Materials Science and Engineering, PO Box 21, Belmont, VIC 3216, Australia;

² School of Aerospace, Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, RMIT University, PO Box 71, Bundoora, VIC 3083, Australia;

³ CSIRO Materials Science and Engineering, 37 Graham Road, Highett, VIC 3190, Australia

* Corresponding author (menghe.miao@csiro.au)

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1 Introduction

Natural fibres such as the bast fibres from flax, hemp and kenaf plants, are emerging as low cost, lightweight and environmentally superior alternatives to glass fibre as reinforcement for composites. In comparison with glass fibre, these fibres can readily absorb a substantial amount of moisture from the surrounding environment. Moisture has no immediate negative effect on the mechanical properties of bast fibres. Any deterioration happens only after fungus starts to grow in the fibres [1].

Natural fibre composites can absorb many times more water than glass fibre composites [2] and their mechanical properties deteriorate rapidly when used in a wet environment. Kim and Seo [3] subjected sisal/vinyl ester and sisal/epoxy composites to wet-dry cycles and found that the strength of the composites suffered a significant decrease after one cycle but then maintained its strength up until five cycles. On the other hand, Newman [4] reported that woven flax/epoxy composite started to show signs of water damage after the first wet-dry cycle, and the damage became more and more pronounced in subsequent cycles. He attributed the incremental development of cracks in the composite to a physical damage mechanism in which the fibres swell and shrink faster and to a greater extent than the matrix.

Many composite products are made in facilities where the humidity conditions are not controlled. Fig. 1 shows the change of daily average relative humidity in a year during a long draught period in Geelong, Victoria, Australia. The average RH over

the year was about 70% and the daily average RH was rarely below 50%.

We previously reported that high moisture content in natural fibres during composite fabrication reduces the interfacial shear strength of bamboo/vinyl ester composites [5] and hydrophobic treatments of the bamboo reinforcement, such as acetylation, can alleviate this effect [6]. This paper reports our recent study on the influence of moisture content in flax fibre at composite fabrication on the mechanical performance of final flax/polyester composites and damages to the composites caused by prolonged water immersion.

Fig. 1. Change of daily average relative humidity during 2008 in Geelong, Victoria, Australia.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

The flax fibre used in this study was retted and scutched at source, and hackled and drawn into

sliver form in a textile mill in China. A commercial unsaturated polyester resin was used to produce the flax/polyester composite samples.

2.2 Composite Fabrication

The flax slivers were pre-dried in oven and then conditioned to required relative humidity at a constant temperature of 20°C for 24 hours using an air conditioning chamber. The pre-drying procedure minimizes the effect of hysteresis in moisture absorption and the 24h conditioning duration ensures the fibres to reach equilibrium moisture content at the required RH levels. The conditioned slivers were impregnated with the unsaturated polyester resin, placed in a die and cured under pressure to produce an essentially unidirectional flax fibre/unsaturated polyester composite. The fibre fraction (approximately 50% by weight) was determined from the dry fibre weight and the final composite weight.

2.3 Composite Testing

The test specimens were cut along the fibre direction from the final composites. Inter-laminar shear strength (ILSS) was tested according to ASTM D 2344. Flexural properties were tested according to ASTM D 790.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Moisture Absorption by Flax Fibre

The moisture absorption of flax fibre initially followed an approximately linear relationship with the square root of time (Fickian diffusion) and then slowed down as the moisture content approached its equilibrium, as shown in Fig. 2. The cellulose molecule of the flax fibre contains hydroxyl groups (hydrophilic) that form hydrogen bonds with water molecules. The first water molecules are absorbed directly onto these hydrophilic groups. These directly attached water molecules become firmly fixed to the fibre molecule structure. As more water molecules are absorbed, they may be attracted to other hydrophilic groups or form further layers on top of the water molecules already absorbed.

The equilibrium moisture absorption of flax fibre increased with the surrounding relative humidity steadily up till about 70% RH and then accelerated rapidly at high relative humidity (above 80% RH), as shown in Fig. 3. This relationship agrees well

with the moisture absorption model proposed by Pierce [7]. Dry flax fibres can absorb more than 10% of moisture in less than an hour in an unconditioned room on a humid day (RH>90%).

Fig. 2. Flax fibre moisture absorption curve at 80% RH and 20°C.

Fig. 3. Equilibrium moisture absorption of flax sliver at different levels of relative humidity.

3.2 Influence of Fabrication Humidity

As shown in Fig. 4, low levels of RH (below 40%) during flax/polyester composite fabrication had a relatively low impact on the interfacial strength of the final composites. High RH levels (above 70%) predisposed the final composites to significantly more damage. Overall, the reduction of ILSS in flax/polyester composite due to moisture absorption was relatively low when compared with the decrease of IFSS in bamboo/vinyl ester composites

measured by pull-out test [5]. The presence of water molecules occupies the sites of hydroxyl groups in the flax fibre and thus inhibits the formation of bonds between the fibre and the matrix, leading to the reduction of interfacial strength. In a previous study [5], we designed an experiment to show that the differential dimensional expansion between cellulosic fibre and polymer matrix due to moisture absorption had little impact on the deterioration of interfacial shear strength (IFSS) in bamboo/vinyl ester composites.

The correlation between interlaminar shear strength and flexural strength and modulus of the flax/polyester composite are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4. Interlaminar shear strength of composites fabricated at different RH conditions.

Fig. 5. Correlation between interlaminar shear strength and flexural properties due to moisture in flax during fabrication.

3.3 Water Immersion

Flax fibre and polyester matrix exhibit different moisture absorption properties. In low fibre content composites, the natural fibres are encapsulated by matrix and thus the fibres can be considered to be isolated from each other. In such a case, water molecules diffuse through the micro-gaps between polymer chains, the gaps and flaws at the fibre-matrix interface and the matrix cracks formed during the compounding process. In composites with a high natural fibre content, the mechanisms for low fibre content composites still operate. In addition, many natural fibres contact with each other and form an interconnected network. Water can thus be transported through fibre-to-fibre direct contacts. Wang et al. [8] have modeled this latter moisture absorption mechanism using percolation theory.

Fig. 6. Specimen weight gain as a result of water immersion.

Fig. 7. Composite volume expansion due to water immersion.

Figs. 6 and 7 show the weight gain and volume expansion of the flax/UP composites in relation to the duration of immersion in water. Saturation was achieved in a period of approximately one week.

As shown in Fig. 8, damage to the final composite took place as soon as the specimens were immersed in water. After the initial period of three days, the interlaminar shear strength tended to decline slowly. The residual ILSS after 43 days of water immersion was about a half of the original ILSS. In comparison, the deterioration of flexural modulus was over 72% while that of flexural strength was about 40%.

Fig. 8. Interlaminar shear strength of composites after water immersion.

Fig. 9. Correlation between interlaminar shear strength and flexural properties due to water immersion.

Because the composite samples were immersed in water continuously and tested for ILSS without

drying, the deterioration of interfacial strength could not be attributed to the swelling-and-shrinking crack development mechanism suggested for repeated wet-dry cycles [4]. Instead, the water molecules absorbed by the flax in the composites form hydrogen bonds with the hydroxyl groups in the fibre, causing scission and weakening of the fibre/matrix interfacial bonds existing in the composite, leading to the decrease of interlaminar shear strength.

The correlations between ILSS of the water immersion samples and their flexural strength and modulus are shown in Fig. 9.

4 Conclusions

Moisture absorption is a major concern for natural fibers used as reinforcement in structural composites. We studied the influences of moisture absorption during flax/polyester composite fabrication and post-fabrication water damages on the mechanical performance of final composites. The interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of the resultant composite could decrease by 45% as a result of high fabrication humidity (80% RH and higher). Damage to final composites due to water immersion was most severe in the first three to four days. Further damages to the composites then slowed down dramatically after the initial period. The cumulative damage to ILSS due to water immersion for 43 days amounted to about 50%. So, a humid day during fabrication causes as much damage to the final composites as soaking the composites in water for an extended period of time.

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